

Exploring Principal Component Analysis in Defect Prediction: A Survey

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Abstract: *The performance of the defect prediction is solely based on the dataset which consist of software metrics. The software metrics or features sometimes very huge in number that makes the dataset complicated and it impacts the classifier or regressor efficiency. The dimension reduction technique is used to solve the problem of massive dimension of features. One of the most commonly used methods to deal with this issue is Principal Component Analysis (PCA). It is a statistical technique used for dimensionality reduction of the vast dataset in machine learning. Large number of research has been taken to predict the defective modules using principal component analysis. Its main function is to reduce the large number of features by extracting the uncorrelated features into groups. It helps to get simpler dataset, easy to handle and visualize, sometime in the cost of accuracy. In line with this, computation complexity of the predictors reduces and takes less time for execution. This survey paper is the exploration of the various studies conducted using principal component analysis for the defect prediction. The survey presented based on 28 studies from 2002 to 2020. It includes topics related to pre-release or post-release defects in software and machine equipment's related defects. The primary focus of this study is to examine the significance of principal component analysis, its contribution in defect prediction and to identify the expansion in this topic. The study will provide helpful outlines of this subject to on-topic scholars and experts.*

Keywords: *Defect Prediction Model; Principal Component Analysis; Feature Selection; Dimension Reduction; Machine Learning Algorithms; Eigenvector; Eigenvalue*

I. INTRODUCTION

The data has been the central point in the machine learning which contains huge number of features. In such situation, it is preferred to analyze the data and minimize the dimension of data to improve the efficiency and accuracy of the model. So, here dimension of data means the number of features or variables or attribute that are considered on each sample or record [3]. The problem “Big p Small n” [1] where dimension reduction is required because it has the number of features ‘p’ greater than the number of records ‘n’. Statistically the number of records

should be exponent to the count of features. But practically in some cases, the dimension of the features has increased.

The two ways of representation of data shown in Fig. 1, where X denotes records and Y denotes the features. Fig. 1a shows the problem of big p and small n where the number of features are large than number of records and Fig. 1b shows the statistical case where $p < n$. Fig. 1a also shows the popular problem called as the curse of dimensionality [1][4] which degrades the performance of the machine learning algorithm. The dimension reduction is one of the important steps in data pre-processing which eliminates the dimension of features. It identifies the relevant reduced set of dimensional representation without missing the information out of the original dataset [2]. Another significant point is that not all features are crucial for training the model. Before constructing any predictive model, we need to reduce the original data dimension without losing the important information [3]. This helps to keep the performance of model and handle the vast datasets.

The key motive of the dimension reduction is sum up as follows:

- The determination of the relevant reduced set of features those are useful for outcomes.
- Decrease the training time of the model.
- To preserve the important characteristics between features.
- To make visualization of high dimension more feasible and similar by mapping it to the lower dimension.
- Save the memory space.
- It checks the multicollinearity by removing the redundant features of same characteristics. For example, ‘performed exercise in minutes’ and ‘fats burnt’ are the features correlated with each other. They provide same kind of information of how much calories burnt. Hence, no need to store both the variable, one of them is sufficient [4].

